

Analysis of the annual fluctuations of the Pioneer 10 signal frequency for compliance with the metric describing the gravitational field of a moving spherical body

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Abstract. The gravitational field of a spherical body moving uniformly and rectilinearly is considered. The corresponding metric for weak gravity is obtained by applying the Lorentz transformations to the linearized isotropic Schwarzschild metric. The change in the flow of time obtained from the geodesic equations is consistent with the annual fluctuations in the frequency of the signal from Pioneer 10.

INTRODUCTION

The Schwarzschild metric describes the gravitational field of a static spherical body. The linearized isotropic Schwarzschild metric is identical to the the perturbed Minkowski metric as a special case of perturbative general relativity with a choice of Newtonian gauge [1]. The special theory of relativity, based on Lorentz transformations, has a number of experimental confirmations. Application of Lorentz transformations to the linearized isotropic Schwarzschild metric was done in [2], where the resulting metric is used to determine the active gravitational mass of a rarefied gas cloud of relativistic particles. Formally, this approach is consistent with gauge theories of gravity, in which gravity is considered as a field in flat Minkowski space [3, 4]. But we will not make such a strong restriction in general, limiting ourselves to the assumption that such an examination is possible from the point of view of a coordinate reference system [5]- [7].

In present paper the geodesic equations for the resulting metric are used to analyze the frequency shift data of the Pioneer 10 signal [8, 9]. It is proposed that the annual frequency variations are caused by a change in time flow on the apparatus from the point of view of an observer on Earth.

APPLYING LORENTZ TRANSFORMATIONS TO SCHWARZSCHILD METRIC

The perturbed Minkowski metric in the Newtonian gauge has the form of the linearized isotropic Schwarzschild metric

$$ds^2 = c^2 \left(1 - \frac{\alpha}{r}\right) dt^2 - \left(1 + \frac{\alpha}{r}\right) (dx^2 + dy^2 + dz^2), \quad (1)$$

where radius is $r = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + z^2}$ and the condition $\alpha/r = o(1)$ is met. At low velocity, the accelerations of a material particle along the coordinates follow from the geodesic equations are

$$\frac{d^2 t}{ds^2} = -\frac{\alpha}{r^2} \frac{dt}{ds} \frac{dr}{ds} \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{d^2 r}{ds^2} = -\frac{\alpha}{2r^2} \left(\frac{d(ct)}{ds}\right)^2, \quad (3)$$

without small quantities of higher orders. After Lorentz transformations, when the observer moves along the coordinate x with velocity v ,

$$t = \frac{t' + \frac{v}{c}x'}{\sqrt{1 - \beta^2}}, \quad x = \frac{x' + vt'}{\sqrt{1 - \beta^2}}, \quad y = y', \quad z = z' \quad (4)$$

with the notation $\beta = v/c$ metric takes the form

$$ds^2 = c^2 \left(1 - \frac{1 + \beta^2 \alpha}{1 - \beta^2 r'} \right) dt'^2 - \frac{4v}{1 - \beta^2 r'} \frac{\alpha}{r'} dt' dx' - \left(1 + \frac{1 + \beta^2 \alpha}{1 - \beta^2 r'} \right) dx'^2 - \left(1 + \frac{\alpha}{r'} \right) (dy'^2 + dz'^2), \quad (5)$$

with the designation

$$r' = \sqrt{\left(\frac{x' + vr'}{\sqrt{1 - \beta^2}} \right)^2 + y'^2 + z'^2}. \quad (6)$$

Geodesics equations [10] for this metric are

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^2 t'}{ds^2} - \frac{c\alpha^2\beta(\beta^2 + 1)x'}{(\beta^2 - 1)^2 r'^4} \left(\frac{dt'}{ds} \right)^2 - \frac{\alpha(\beta^2 + 1)x'[(\beta^2 - 1)r' - \alpha(\beta^2 + 1)]}{(\beta^2 - 1)^2 r'^4} \frac{dt'}{ds} \frac{dx'}{ds} \\ - \frac{\alpha y'[(\beta^2 + 1)r' + \alpha(1 - \beta^2)]}{(\beta^2 - 1)r'^4} \frac{dt'}{ds} \frac{dy'}{ds} - \frac{\alpha z'[(\beta^2 + 1)r' + \alpha(1 - \beta^2)]}{(\beta^2 - 1)r'^2(r'^2 - \alpha^2)} \frac{dt'}{ds} \frac{dz'}{ds} \\ - \frac{2\alpha\beta x'[(\beta^2 - 1)r' - \alpha(\beta^2 + 1)]}{c(\beta^2 - 1)^2 r'^4} \left(\frac{dx'}{ds} \right)^2 - \frac{2\alpha\beta y'}{c(\beta^2 - 1)r'^3} \frac{dx'}{ds} \frac{dy'}{ds} \\ - \frac{2\alpha\beta z'}{c(\beta^2 - 1)r'^3} \frac{dx'}{ds} \frac{dz'}{ds} - \frac{\alpha^2\beta x'}{c(\beta^2 - 1)r'^4} \left[\left(\frac{dy'}{ds} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{dz'}{ds} \right)^2 \right] = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^2 x'}{ds^2} + \frac{c^2\alpha(\beta^2 + 1)x'[(\beta^2 - 1)r' + \alpha(\beta^2 + 1)]}{2(\beta^2 - 1)^2 r'^4} \left(\frac{dt'}{ds} \right)^2 - \frac{2c\alpha^2\beta(\beta^2 + 1)x'}{(\beta^2 - 1)^2 r'^4} \frac{dt'}{ds} \frac{dx'}{ds} \\ + \frac{2c\alpha\beta y'}{(\beta^2 - 1)r'^3} \frac{dt'}{ds} \frac{dy'}{ds} + \frac{2c\alpha\beta z'}{(\beta^2 - 1)r'^3} \frac{dt'}{ds} \frac{dz'}{ds} + \frac{\alpha x'[(\beta^4 - 1)r' + \alpha(\beta^4 - 6\beta^2 + 1)]}{2(\beta^2 - 1)^2 r'^4} \left(\frac{dx'}{ds} \right)^2 \\ + \frac{\alpha y'[(\beta^2 + 1)r' - \alpha(1 - \beta^2)]}{(\beta^2 - 1)^2 r'^4} \frac{dx'}{ds} \frac{dy'}{ds} + \frac{\alpha z'[(\beta^2 + 1)r' - \alpha(1 - \beta^2)]}{(\beta^2 - 1)^2 r'^4} \frac{dx'}{ds} \frac{dz'}{ds} \\ + \frac{\alpha x'[(\beta^2 - 1)r' + \alpha(\beta^2 + 1)]}{(\beta^2 - 1)r'^4} \left[\left(\frac{dy'}{ds} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{dz'}{ds} \right)^2 \right] = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^2 y'}{ds^2} - \frac{c^2\alpha(\beta^2 + 1)y'}{2(\beta^2 - 1)r'^3} \left(\frac{dt'}{ds} \right)^2 - \frac{2c\alpha\beta y'}{(\beta^2 - 1)r'^3} \frac{dt'}{ds} \frac{dx'}{ds} - \frac{\alpha(\beta^2 + 1)y'}{2(\beta^2 - 1)r'^3} \left(\frac{dx'}{ds} \right)^2 \\ - \frac{\alpha x' dx' dy'}{r'^3 ds ds} - \frac{\alpha z' dz' dy'}{r'^3 ds ds} - \frac{\alpha y'}{2r'^3} \left[\left(\frac{dy'}{ds} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{dz'}{ds} \right)^2 \right] = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{d^2 z'}{ds^2} - \frac{c^2\alpha(\beta^2 + 1)z'}{2(\beta^2 - 1)r'^3} \left(\frac{dt'}{ds} \right)^2 - \frac{2c\alpha\beta z'}{(\beta^2 - 1)r'^3} \frac{dt'}{ds} \frac{dx'}{ds} - \frac{\alpha(\beta^2 + 1)z'}{2(\beta^2 - 1)r'^3} \left(\frac{dx'}{ds} \right)^2$$

$$-\frac{\alpha x'}{r'^3} \frac{dx'}{ds} \frac{dz'}{ds} - \frac{\alpha y'}{r'^3} \frac{dz'}{ds} \frac{dy'}{ds} - \frac{\alpha z'}{2r'^3} \left[\left(\frac{dz'}{ds} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{dy'}{ds} \right)^2 \right] = 0. \quad (10)$$

The terms containing α^2 not reflect the properties of space-time due to the linearization of the metric. To consider them to be small, we assume $\frac{\alpha\beta x'}{r'} = o\left(\left|x' \frac{dx'}{ds}\right| + \left|y' \frac{dy'}{ds}\right| + \left|z' \frac{dz'}{ds}\right|\right)$. Due to the low gravity under condition $\beta = o(1)$, the accelerations take an approximate form

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^2 t'}{ds^2} &= -\frac{\alpha x'}{r'^3} \frac{dt'}{ds} \frac{dx'}{ds} - \frac{\alpha y'}{r'^3} \frac{dt'}{ds} \frac{dy'}{ds} - \frac{\alpha z'}{r'^3} \frac{dt'}{ds} \frac{dz'}{ds} \\ &\quad - \frac{2\alpha\beta x'}{cr'^3} \left(\frac{dx'}{ds} \right)^2 - \frac{2\alpha\beta y'}{cr'^3} \frac{dx'}{ds} \frac{dy'}{ds} - \frac{2\alpha\beta z'}{cr'^3} \frac{dx'}{ds} \frac{dz'}{ds}, \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^2 x'}{ds^2} &= -\frac{c^2 \alpha x'}{2r'^3} \left(\frac{dt'}{ds} \right)^2 + \frac{2c\alpha\beta y'}{r'^3} \frac{dt'}{ds} \frac{dy'}{ds} + \frac{2c\alpha\beta z'}{r'^3} \frac{dt'}{ds} \frac{dz'}{ds} + \frac{\alpha x'}{2r'^3} \left(\frac{dx'}{ds} \right)^2 \\ &\quad - \frac{\alpha y'}{r'^3} \frac{dx'}{ds} \frac{dy'}{ds} - \frac{\alpha z'}{r'^3} \frac{dx'}{ds} \frac{dz'}{ds} - \frac{\alpha x'}{r'^3} \left[\left(\frac{dy'}{ds} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{dz'}{ds} \right)^2 \right], \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^2 y'}{ds^2} &= -\frac{c^2 \alpha y'}{2r'^3} \left(\frac{dt'}{ds} \right)^2 - \frac{2c\alpha\beta y'}{r'^3} \frac{dt'}{ds} \frac{dx'}{ds} - \frac{\alpha y'}{2r'^3} \left(\frac{dx'}{ds} \right)^2 \\ &\quad + \frac{\alpha x'}{r'^3} \frac{dx'}{ds} \frac{dy'}{ds} + \frac{\alpha z'}{r'^3} \frac{dz'}{ds} \frac{dy'}{ds} + \frac{\alpha y'}{2r'^3} \left[\left(\frac{dy'}{ds} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{dz'}{ds} \right)^2 \right], \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^2 z'}{ds^2} &= -\frac{c^2 \alpha z'}{2r'^3} \left(\frac{dt'}{ds} \right)^2 - \frac{2c\alpha\beta z'}{r'^3} \frac{dt'}{ds} \frac{dx'}{ds} - \frac{\alpha z'}{2r'^3} \left(\frac{dx'}{ds} \right)^2 \\ &\quad + \frac{\alpha x'}{r'^3} \frac{dx'}{ds} \frac{dz'}{ds} + \frac{\alpha y'}{r'^3} \frac{dz'}{ds} \frac{dy'}{ds} + \frac{\alpha z'}{2r'^3} \left[\left(\frac{dz'}{ds} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{dy'}{ds} \right)^2 \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

For small velocities, $\frac{dx'}{ds} = o(1)$, $\frac{dy'}{ds} = o(1)$, $\frac{dz'}{ds} = o(1)$, accelerations of the time flow and motion along the space coordinates will be

$$\frac{d^2 t'}{ds^2} = -\frac{\alpha x}{r'^3} \frac{dt'}{ds} \frac{dx'}{ds} - \frac{\alpha y}{r'^3} \frac{dt'}{ds} \frac{dy'}{ds} - \frac{\alpha z}{r'^3} \frac{dt'}{ds} \frac{dz'}{ds} \quad (15)$$

$$\frac{d^2 x'}{ds^2} = -x' \frac{\alpha}{2r'^3} \left(\frac{d(ct')}{ds} \right)^2, \quad (16)$$

$$\frac{d^2 y'}{ds^2} = -y' \frac{\alpha}{2r'^3} \left(\frac{d(ct')}{ds} \right)^2, \quad (17)$$

$$\frac{d^2 z'}{ds^2} = -z' \frac{\alpha}{2r'^3} \left(\frac{d(ct')}{ds} \right)^2, \quad (18)$$

without small quantities of higher orders.

FIGURE 1. Ecliptic pole view of Pioneer 10 trajectory, [8].

ANALYSIS OF THE PIONEER 10 SIGNAL FREQUENCY SHIFT

Expected additional acceleration of Pioneer 10 is determined under assumption that signal frequency shift is caused by the Doppler effect [8, 9]. Distances to the apparatus and accelerations are shown on the flight diagram Fig. 1 and graph of the periodic component of acceleration, Fig. 2. It has annual periodic component with an amplitude $2.4_{-0.5}^{+1.5} * 10^{-8} cm^2/s$ at a distance of 40 AU (1987) and $(1.5 \pm 1) * 10^{-8} cm^2/s$ for 53 AU (1992).

The total additional constant acceleration was found from the formula relating the calculated frequency of the received signal to the observed one [9]:

$$V_{obs} = V_{model} * (1 - a_p * t/c) \quad (19)$$

assuming that this is caused by the acceleration of the spacecraft itself. However, the same effect will be produced by time dilation on it calculated by the formula

$$V_{obs} = V_{model} * (1 - c \int_s^{s_0} \frac{d^2t}{ds^2} ds) \quad (20)$$

for $s \approx ct$.

Let us establish that the x -axis is directed from the Sun to the Pioneer 10 apparatus and the x' -axis is parallel to it and begins on the Earth. The velocity $u = \frac{dx'}{ds}$ is calculated as follows:

$$u = u_p + u_E \cos(\omega t' + \phi_0), \quad (21)$$

where u_p is the velocity of the Pioneer relative to the Sun, u_E is orbital velocity of the Earth, ω is the period of the Earth's revolution around the Sun, and ϕ_0 is the initial angle. Calculations using formula (15), when converted to

FIGURE 2. The Pioneer 10 Doppler data: 50-day averages of anomalous acceleration – January 1987 to July 1998. Best-fit constant component of anomalous acceleration removed [9].

acceleration for the periodic component, yield $3.7 * 10^{-8} cm^2/s$ at a distance of 40 AE and $2.05 * 10^{-8} cm^2/s$ for 53 AE. These values are within the error limits of the periodic acceleration amplitudes determined from the Pioneer 10 signal frequency.

CONCLUSION

The annual frequency variations of Pioneer 10 signal are consistent with the assumption of a change in the time flow on the apparatus from the point of view of an observer on Earth. This follows from the properties of the space-time obtained by applying Lorentz transformations to the linearized isotropic Schwarzschild metric. Analysis of data on frequency changes received from a spacecraft located at a distance of 40-60 astronomical units confirms this approach.

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